

Discover your Guinness Story

Repurposing a digital preservation system into a historical database

The Guinness Archive partnered with Ancestry in 2023 to digitise and transcribe 1,315 personnel and trade ledgers. The project resulted in 250,000 digital images (7TB), and over 1.6 million individual data entries. The Archive embarked on a project to create a user-friendly database within a digital preservation environment. Digital preservation systems represent a significant investment for any memory institution and this provided the Archive with an opportunity to use it to meet additional business needs.

Considerations

Preservica only system at Archive's disposal that could comfortably store and process 7TB.

Internal stakeholders request that access was via the Guinness Storehouse website. Maximum load time of website needed to be maintained.

Create user-friendly genealogical database, returning transcribed information and digitised images.

Approach

Ingest

Package digital objects and metadata using Preservica's Open Preservation Exchange (OPEX) format and Preservation Asset eXchange (PAX) protocol for ingest. Link to Axiell Collections catalogue.

Create metadata fragments

Create a metadata fragment for each line of data and package it with its associated digital object (or ledger image). The nature of the ledgers as day-to-day records meant that a single image could be associated with tens of individual fragments.

Develop API

Fragments made the images searchable within Preservica using the personal names, addresses and dates. An API call was developed using Preservica's developer tools to run searches entered by the user in the GSH website interface.

Stumbling blocks

Initial results from this approach were mixed. The API was successful in being able to retrieve metadata fragments but, in cases where a fragment field was empty, data would be 'bumped up' from the next fragment, creating mismatches.

A different approach - Data as record

Re-ingest each line of csv data as an individual 'record' within Preservica and link to digital image via UUID. We mapped the API search to the fields we wanted to be publicly searchable, and testing proved that this solution had been successful.

Image retrieval

Initial attempts to display images using third-party image viewers were unsuccessful. The web tech team were eventually able to use the API to generate a thumbnail representation of the image hosted in Preservica.

Test & Launch

Search went live in March 2025 following several rounds of internal testing.

Results

Significant success in terms of harnessing available resources to create a user-friendly historical database for our users.

Increased accessibility of collections.

Bolsters the business case for continued investment in digital preservation system. Diversifies functionality.

Average monthly visitors: 1,112, avg. 1m and 14s

Peak monthly visitors: 15,017, avg. 1m and 52s

Learnings

Delivery of data

Define preferred delivery method of project outputs from the outset.

Third-party communication

Ensure that any developers remain in constant communication with the vendor. Digital preservation software is bespoke and specific functionalities or quirks may not be immediately apparent to IT professionals. A lot of trial and error was avoidable.